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1 M3.5 - Mapping of PID policies for different stakeholders

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/A cronym	Description
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
HPC	High-Performance Computing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PHIDIAS	Prototype of HPC/Data Infrastructure for On-demand Services
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EOSC PID TF	EOSC PID Policy and Implementation Task Force (https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/pid-policy-implementation/)
PID Ecosystem	Collection of standards, services, actors, and roles that enable a specific PID Stack to provide a service, together with the specific end users of the PID Stack.
PID Stack	Collection of services, supported by standardization, resolution mechanisms, and namespace management that results in a branded or unique PID service to PID Managers.
PID	Persistent Identifier
POSI	Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure

4 Introduction

Work Package 3 of the FAIR-IMPACT project, titled Persistent identifiers, has the objective to “work with PID service providers and infrastructures to meet user needs, align with EOSC policy and maximize uptake”. Task 3.3 of this work package is focused on “EOSC PID policy alignment and support” and will produce Deliverable 3.5 “Guidelines for creating a user tailored EOSC compliant PID policy” in month 24 of the project.

This milestone is an intermediate step towards the provisioning of Deliverable 3.5 and will report on a number of inventories, mappings, best practices and classifications of components and related issues of the PID ecosystem with a focus on the EOSC PID Policy. The activities were carried out in close cooperation with the FAIRCORE4EOSC project and more specifically the work done by work package 2 on the “compliance assessment toolkit” of the EOSC PID policy.

The means of verification of this milestone is defined as “mapping is available”. In close cooperation with the FAIRCORE4EOSC project inventories, best practices and literature were collected, analyzed and discussed with stakeholders (such as the EOSC PID TF). An overview of these activities is reported in this milestone document.

Task 3.3 has also contributed to the review of the conceptual model, the service specifications and helped inventorize the PID ecosystem through, for example, engaging with stakeholders such as the EOSC PID TF.

5 Description of the Milestone

Milestone 3.5 concerns the mapping of PID policies for different stakeholders (with an emphasis on PID managers, see table). An inventory of PID policies and related topics was carried out during the beginning of both the FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC projects. This inventory and analysis will be extended and harmonized periodically during the lifespan of the projects. To formulate this milestone, a snapshot of the most relevant inventories and analyses is presented and provided with contextual information.

An overview of the actors and stakeholders is provided in D2.1 Compliance Assessment Specification¹, as shown below:

Table 7 – Actors and Stakeholders, User Roles

Actor	Description
PID Standards Body	A PID Standardisation organisation (IETF, IANA, The DONA Foundation, ISO) which appoints the PID Authority and is responsible for the PID Scheme.
PID Scheme (Component)	A set of rules and standards defining the nature of a PID. This would include a set of lexical formatting rules for PIDs within a namespace. It could also define for example: associated PID Type; definition of associated metadata; quality assurance conditions; usage rights, terms and conditions, and algorithmic methods for generating PID names and enforcing PID properties.
PID Authority (Role)	A controller responsible for maintaining the rules for defining the integrity of PIDs within a PID Scheme. These rules may include setting standards for lexical formats, algorithms, and protocols to ensure global uniqueness, together with setting quality of service conditions to enforce compliance to the rules. PID Authorities may be organisations (e.g., DOI.org), which enforce control over a PID infrastructure. A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) 8 may also be Authorities which do not have a central control (for example Software Heritage persistent identifiers ¹ and W3C's Decentralised Identifiers), but provide a community standardisation mechanism that specifies the conformance of PIDs to a PID Scheme.
PID Service Provider (Role)	An organisation which provides PID services in conformance to a PID Scheme, subject to its PID Authority. PID Service Providers have responsibility for the provision, integrity, reliability, and scalability of PID Services, in particular the issuing and resolution of PIDs, but also lookup and search services, and interoperability with a generic resolution system.
Multi-Primary Administrator (MPA)(Role)	"Each credentialed MPA operates its own GHR Services in accordance with the DONA Foundation Policies & Procedures for the GHR and coordinates its GHR Services with other MPAs and DONA in the distributed operation of the GHR on a multi-primary basis." (DOI and Handle Only)
PID Service (Component)	Basic services are those that create, manage, and resolve PIDs and their associated kernel information which conforms to a PID Scheme. Advanced, value-added services may also be provided, for example attribute search or metrics.

¹ D2.1 Compliance Assessment Specification. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10067253> (pp. 21-23)

PID Manager (Role)	PID Managers have responsibilities to maintain the integrity of the relationship between entities and their PIDs, in conformance to a PID Scheme defined by a PID Authority. A PID Manager will typically subscribe to PID services to offer functionality to PID Owners within the PID Manager's services. One example is a Service Provider which uses PID Services as part of its own service delivery. For example, PID Managers may include a provider of a data repository, a data catalogue, or a research workflow system.
PID Owner (Role)	An actor (an organisation or individual) who has the authority to create a PID, assign PID to an entity, provide and maintain accurate Kernel Information for the PID. A new PID Owner must be identified, and these responsibilities transferred, if the current PID Owner is no longer able to carry them out.
End User (Role)	The end user of PID Services, for example researchers, or software, or services produced to support researchers.
Compliance Monitoring (Role)	On completion, the work will support an additional role and associated component for the EOSC PID Policy, as follows: Compliance Monitoring (Role) - One or more organisations that provide services to monitor and/or enforce compliance (with PID Policy), resulting in interoperable and aggregable compliance metrics for the roles and components foreseen in the policy.
Casual User/ General Public	Users that engage with the system to search for and find existing evaluation records, statistics, and guidance in respect of compliance.
Identified User	Users may want to specify preferences and save context, and to do so, users need to be identified unambiguously. No other information is needed except some globally unique identifier.
Validated User	Users that contributed external evaluations and assessments and may want to contribute a self-assessment. These users will often want to obtain additional guidance and best practices for the elements where their level of performance is lower than the benchmarks. These users can have any of the detailed roles identified in 01 to 08 above.
Admin User	Administrative users that manage vocabularies, users, and databases associated with the CAT.

Table: Actors and Stakeholder, User Roles

The actors and stakeholders in the table are a part of the PID ecosystem that also contains the relations between them. This is visualized in the model below, based on Hugo, W. et al (2023) p 15).²

² The model is an updated version of the model published in (Hugo, W. et al (2023)).

Ecosystem Entities and Relations (updated version)

FAIR-IMPACT T3.3 has created a first version of an inventory and classification of elements, characteristics and attributes of PID Stacks. It consolidates community expectations, assertions and features advertised by various PID Stacks as well as the content of the EOSC PID Policy into a multi-level hierarchy.

The inventory is available in the form of a Mindmap³ and will be further developed in the project. A screenshot of the Mindmap is provided below. The blue components of the Mindmap are based on the EOSC PID policy (Hellström, M., et al (2020)). The yellow components are based on the POSI (Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure).

³ A Mindmap is a diagram used to visually organize information into a hierarchy, showing relationships among pieces of the whole

Mindmap: Elements, Characteristics and Attributes of PID Stacks.⁴

5.1 Role of the milestone

This milestone is important for the collection and analysis of information resources, which is required to realize the main deliverable of T3.3, D3.5 “Guidelines for creating a user tailored EOSC compliant PID policy”. To meet this end, the mapping exercise of the current PID ecosystem and assessing the EOSC PID policy is of critical importance.

5.1.1 Means of verification

The most important way to verify the mappings of this milestone is to get feedback from key players in the field.

The EOSC PID TF plays an important role here. An informal meeting, initiated by T3.3 of the FAIR-IMPACT project, was held with the task force on November 7th 2023, though it must be noted that only a small number of task force members were able to participate. A main topic of discussion in the meeting was to get input from the EOSC PID TF on the assessment of the

⁴ Link to live version of the Mindmap:
https://atlas.mindmup.com/scientilla/f43_4_1_pid_essential_elements/index.html (accessed, Nov 27, 2023)

EOSC PID Policy⁵ based on the compliant assessment specification created by the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. The recommendations for improvement to the EOSC PID Policy (that are part of the assessment) were also covered during the meeting. To what extent the recommendations are acknowledged and supported by the EOSC PID TF is not yet clear as the TF needs more time to evaluate them. It is also not yet clear whether the TF has the resources available to do this or even whether the EOSC PID TF will be active in 2024, as their official mandate ends in 2023. FAIR-IMPACT has informed the EOSC PID TF that support actions provided by the FAIR-IMPACT project will be available next year which might provide the possibility to further evaluate the recommendations.

Another independent avenue of verification are workshops with stakeholders such as the FAIR-IMPACT workshop “EOSC Compliant PID Implementations - Practical Guidelines for Implementing Best Practices”, organized on November 21st 2023 in collaboration with FAIR-IMPACT T3.4.⁶

⁵ [F.43.3.1.1 Assessment - EOSC PID Policy](#) (accessed, Nov 27, 2023)

⁶ See:

<https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/eosc-compliant-pid-implementations-practical-guidelines-implementing-best> (accessed, Nov 27, 2023)

6 Conclusions and next steps

This Milestone reports on initial mappings of PID policies and available related material and will be expanded upon in the coming months. In terms of next steps, the focus will be on communication with key players in the PID ecosystem, especially PID managers.⁷ The organization and reporting of workshops and other meetings will continue (ref. Milestone 3.6 “3 PID policy alignment workshops & feedback report”, due in month 24). The main focus will be on compliance assessment of PID policies. Activities will be carried out in close cooperation with the other tasks in WP3 in FAIR-IMPACT as well as WP2 in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.

The process is contextualized further in the diagram below.

- Step 1: The EOSC PID Policy serves as an input for both FAIRCORE4EOSC (for development of the Compliance Assessment Toolkit) and FAIR-IMPACT (providing implications for and best practices with respect to institutional and national PID Policies).
- Step 2: The FAIRCORE4EOSC project (WP2) conducted an in-depth assessment of the EOSC PID Policy with an eye on structuring and encoding it to enable compliance assessment. This resulted in a set of proposed improvements to the policy, that were

⁷ See: Table 1: Actors and Stakeholders, User Roles (p. 8)

shared with the EOSC PID TF, and will serve as the basis for future work by both FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT.

- Step 3: FAIR-IMPACT has commenced with a series of community engagement initiatives (ongoing) and a literature review of the PID landscape to document and characterize community expectations, use cases and workflows, the current scope and nature of PID policies and references to PID use in selected data policies. From this, it is possible to create three interrelated knowledge bases:
 - An inventory of the elements, characteristics, and features of PIDs as offered by PID services;
 - A similar inventory of user community expectations, defined by use cases, workflows, and benefits;
 - A set of best practices and guidelines for specific actors in the PID ecosystem, which can be used as the basis of national, institutional, and service level policies, and will be used as a basis for guidance in the Compliance Assessment Toolkit.

This work will feed into the final content of the Compliance Assessment Toolkit and its corresponding knowledge base: allowing actors in the ecosystem to evaluate compliance with the EOSC PID Policy as well as providing guidance and communicating best practices to all actors, including end users.

7 References

Hugo, W., Steinhoff, W., Turner, D., Buys, M., & Zamani, T. (2023). D2.1 Compliance Assessment Specification. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10067253>

Hellström, M., Heughebaert, A., Kotarski, R. et al., A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/926037>